

LONG TERM AGING OF IMPLANTED SILICONE/SILICA COMPOSITE BREAST IMPLANTS

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SUMMARY: A comprehensive study is being conducted to investigate the changes in the mechanical and chemical properties of composite (silicone/silica) breast implants as a function of implantation time. In the present study the properties of gel-filled explants with in vivo duration times ranging from 4 months to 21 years are compared to control samples. Tensile strength and elongation were measured for both explant and control shells using identical testing protocols. In addition, the tensile strength and elongation of shells which were extracted with hexane to remove non-cross linked silicones were measured. The chemical composition of the shell extracts was examined by MALDI (matrix assisted laser desorption ionization) mass spectrometry and gas chromatography/mass spectrometry (GC/MS). In addition, swelling measurements were used to determine the average molecular weight between cross-links (and/or entanglements). Low molecular weight silicones with degree of cyclization ranging from 4 to 20 were determined by GC/MS. Linear PDMS with molecular weights up to 12,000 Daltons and cyclics with degrees of cyclization up to 60 were measured by MALDI.

KEYWORDS: aging, durability, silicone elastomers, breast implants.

INTRODUCTION

The use of advanced polymeric and composite materials in biomedical applications has increased tremendously in the past few years. Of particular interest has been the use of composite materials for in vivo applications such as hip joints or artificial body parts. One particular system, silicone breast prostheses (implants), has received considerable notoriety during the past 3-4 years, primarily through the mass communication media and the judicial system. Although breast implants are not usually considered composites, the shell which contains the fluid or gel is a true composite and is composed of a cross-linked silicone rubber containing a fine particulate silica filler. The silicone/silica composite shell is used in almost all breast implants regardless of manufacturer or filling fluid. Implants have been filled with lightly cross-linked silicone gel, saline solution, and soybean oil.

In general, the shells fall into two broad classes typified by Dow Corning Silastic® I and Silastic® II. A silicone dispersion in an appropriate solvent, such as toluene or xylene, containing approximately 16% silica (SiO₂) and a small amount of cross-linking catalyst (such as chloroplatinic acid) is coated on a mandrel and thermally cross-linked after a specified thickness has been applied. The silica is added to increase the mechanical properties of the silicone elastomer. Silastic® I contains only the silicone/silica shell while Silastic® II contains an additional barrier layer of fluorosilicone or diphenylsilicone polymers or copolymers. The extra layer, usually called the "barrier coating" is added to minimize the permeation of gel fluid, typically low molecular weight silicones, through the shell.

The biomedical controversy surrounding the breast implant issue has been primarily concerned with the immunology or effect of silicone fluids on health issues. Our work is concerned with the long-term durability or aging of the silicone/silica composite shell. We have an inventory of approximately 500 explanted breast implants and 400 control implants which were manufactured at various times by different suppliers. The controls were stored in an ambient environment since their fabrication. Silastic® I implants were first used in the early 1970's while the Silastic® II's were first introduced in the early 1980's. Therefore, we have a large series of samples which were aged in vivo for time periods ranging from a few months to more than 20 years. The implants were prepared over a ten year period and as might be expected there is some variation in the exact composition and structure of an implant type even when prepared by a specific manufacturer. This report is restricted to a study of implants prepared by one manufacturer and the associated controls manufactured at approximately the same time. The data can be used to formulate general trends in material properties as a function of real time aging.

The mechanical properties and chemical composition of the silicone/silica composite shells are strongly related. Mechanical properties of specific interest are tensile strength and elongation. These properties are primarily governed by the cross-link density of the elastomer, the effect of plasticizers on the elastomer, and the nature of the silicone-silica interaction. Real-time aging is a combination of both physical and chemical aging. Physical aging includes such phenomena as plasticization while chemical aging is concerned with bond breakage or formation, i.e., cross-linking or degradation.

If the elastomer undergoes a reaction with the environment, i.e., chemical aging, a change in the cross-link density of the elastomer is to be noted. An increase in cross-link density should be accompanied by an increase in modulus and an associated embrittlement of the shell; a decrease in cross-link density suggests degradation of the elastomer and an overall loss in strength. The silica serves as bonding sites for the silicone chains and a loss in the interaction between the silicone and the silica would primarily lead to a decrease in the mechanical strength of the shell. Most of the implants contain a silicone gel with a composition similar to that of the cross-linked shell. The gel contains a large mixture of cyclic and linear silicones with a solubility parameter nearly identical to that of the elastomeric shell. Thus, the overall composition of the low molecular weight silicones, i.e., the non-cross-linked component, and their concentration sorbed by the elastomeric shell during aging is indicative of aging induced changes in the composition of either the shell or the gel which may occur during implantation.

It is particularly important to compare values obtained from a series of samples implanted for various time periods with those of samples prepared at essentially the same time, but not implanted, i.e., control samples. We used a series of mechanical testing and advanced physical chemical methods to analyze explanted samples and compare the results with a similar series of non-implanted specimens.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Samples: The elastomeric shells were wiped clean of the adhering silicone gel by gentle wiping with Kimwipes® moistened with isopropyl alcohol. Both dog-bone shaped samples (for strain/strain analysis) and rectangular pieces (approximately 3x3 cm for swelling measurements) were cut from sections of the shell and their positions were recorded. In general, five dogbone shaped samples were used for mechanical testing and three additional samples were extracted with hexane for the extraction studies.

Extraction of Shells: The samples were extracted in chromatographic grade hexane (Fisher) at 50°C for 96 hours. The samples were carefully dried to constant weight and used for subsequent analysis. The percent extractable was determined from the initial and final weights. The hexane extract was used directly for both GC/MS, and MALDI analysis.

Cross-Link Density: The cross-link density of the elastomer shells was determined by swelling measurements. After hexane extraction, which removes “all” the low molecular weight silicones, shell samples were swollen in toluene to constant weight. The samples were removed from the toluene, patted dry, and placed in a tared glass weighing jar. The cross-link density (v_c) was determined according to the Flory-Rehner theory [2] for polymer swelling:

$$v_c = \left[-\ln(1 - v_p) + v_p + \chi v_p^2 \right] \left[V \left(v_p^{1/3} - \frac{1}{2} v_p \right) \right] \quad (1)$$

where χ is the solvent interaction parameter, v_p is the volume fraction of polymer in the swollen rubber, and V is the molar volume for the swelling agent (for toluene $V = 106 \text{ cm}^3/\text{mol}$). For toluene sorption in PDMS elastomer, $\chi = 0.413 + 0.364 v_p$ [3]. The average molecular weight between cross-links (M_c) is given by the reciprocal of v_c

$$M_c = \frac{\rho}{v_c} \quad (2)$$

where ρ is the density of the polymer. The tensile modulus (Young’s) E for the membrane can also be estimated by the relation

$$E = 3RTv_c \quad (3)$$

where R is the universal gas constant the T is the temperature (K).

MALDI: Matrix assisted laser desorption ionization (MALDI) mass spectrometry is a recent development specifically designed to utilize the tremendous analytical capability of mass spectrometry for the analysis of high molecular weight compounds [4,5]. The MALDI mass spectrometer is a PerSeptive Biosystems Voyager RP with a nominal resolving power of approximately 300 and the upper mass range is approximately 50,000 Da. A few micograms of a polymer extract are placed on an inert matrix, such as 2,5 dinitrobenzoic acid, dried and ionized with a N_2 -laser (338 nm). The radiation is absorbed by the matrix and “transferred” to the polymer, with little or no fragmentation of the molecular ions.

Tensile Testing: Tensile testing was conducted on a minimum of 5 specimens cut with ASTM D412 die D half-scale. [Only 3 samples were measured for the extracted samples.] The tests were conducted to conform to ASTM D412 on an Instron 5583. The elongation data were obtained from grip extension at a cross head speed of 20 in/min.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The stress/strain curves for typical Silastic® I and Silastic® II implant shells are shown in Figure 1. [The ordinate represents the engineering stress.] The curves are nearly identical for low strains but rapidly diverge for strains greater than 200%. Silastic® II exhibits the typical

stress/strain curve expected for a thin elastomer. In general, both the strain-to-failure and the stress-to-failure are considerably larger in Silastic® II controls than observed in Silastic® I controls. The toughness of Silastic® II, i.e., the area under the stress/strain, is also larger than that exhibited by Silastic® I.

The material which is extracted from the shell can result from one or more of four sources: 1) indigenous originally present in the elastomer, 2) diffuse in from the bio-environment, 3) diffuse in from the filling fluid (in this study from the silicone gel), or 4) result from the degradation of the elastomer network. Our analytical method was not designed to identify biomaterials, so case 2) is not applicable to this study. For an aging or long-term durability study, it is not important to distinguish between 1) and 3) but distinguish between indigenous and/or gel and degradation products. It is difficult to separate the compositional changes due to the variability of processing procedures used over a ten-year period (1975-1986 for Silastic® I and 1981-1992 from Silastic® II) from those changes associated with in vivo aging. However, a careful examination of a large number of specimens and controls can lead to meaningful distinction between degradation products and indigenous and/or sorbed compounds.

The strength and elongation of Silastic® I and Silastic® II implants as a function of implantation time are shown in Figures 2 and 3, respectively. Although there is considerable scatter in the data, Silastic® I shows little change in strength after 20 years in vivo, although elongation

Fig. 1. Stress/strain curve for typical as-received Silastic® I and Silastic® II silicone/silica elastomeric shell.

appears to decrease on the order of 20% in the same time interval. However, Silastic® II does appear to exhibit a decrease in both strength and elongation as a function of implantation time. It is important to note that additional long-term data is needed to determine the relationship between the mechanical properties and implantation time. Do the properties decrease linearly with time, or do they reach an asymptotic value? The amount of extractables in Silastic® II shell increases with implantation time, see Figure 4. The increased

swelling of the Silastic® II samples as function of implantation time can account for a large fraction of the property decrease exhibited in Figure 3. The non-cross-linked silicone in the gel in Silastic® I shell reach an equilibrium concentration in a short time, i.e., of the order of months. Because of the barrier coating in Silastic® II, many months, or even years, are required to reach equilibrium. Therefore, the measured properties would appear to decrease even though the elastomeric network was not degraded. A comparison of the changes in mechanical properties of as-received controls and the corresponding extracted samples is given in Table 1. These values are compared to data supplied by the manufacturer on a dispersed elastomer film prepared from the same batch of material used to prepare the implant. The agreement between the values of the extracted shell and elastomeric film data is good. This data supports the hypothesis that the sorbed compounds do not degrade the elastomeric network.

MALDI provides an excellent method to analyze the molecular distribution of the extract. A typical MALDI spectrum from a Silastic® I control is shown in Figure 5. In this particular sample the amount of material extracted from the shell corresponds to 23% of its dry weight. The number average and weight average of the extract are 2618 and 4650 Da, respectively. The insert shows an expanded portion of the mass region from 1050 to 2000 Da. Two series of peaks are clearly visible, each member of the series separated by 74 mass units (corresponding to the basic siloxane unit $[\text{CH}_3)_2\text{SiO}]$. The two series are separated by 14 mass units, a methylene group. These two series correspond to linear and cyclic silicones: the structure of the linear and cyclic molecules are $\text{CH}_3[\text{Si}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{O}]_n \text{Si}(\text{CH}_3)_3$ and $[\text{Si}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{O}]_m$, respectively and are the characteristic materials found in the filling gel.

Fig. 2. Strength and elongation as a function of implantation time for Silastic® I silicone/silica shell implants.

Fig. 3. Strength and elongation as a function of implantation time for Silastic® II silicone shell implants.

The number and weight average molecular weights determined by MALDI for a series of Silastic® I and Silastic® II explants as a function of implantation time are given in Figures 6 and 7, respectively. The values measured for the controls (zero implantation time) vary by 25%. The values observed in Silastic® I are, within experimental error, independent of implantation time. Although additional data is required, the preliminary studies suggest that the average molecular weight of the extract from Silastic® II increases during aging. This latter observation may result from the slow diffusion of non-crosslinked silicones from the gel into the shell.

Fig. 4. Percent extractables (hexane) as a function of implantation time for Silastic® II shells.

Table 1: Comparison of Mechanical Properties of As-Received Shells, Extracted Shells, and Dispersed Elastomer Films*

	Silastic® I	Tensile Strength	
	% Extracted	MPa	% Elongation
As-Received Shell	---	5.63	397
Extracted Shell	17.0	10.86	565
Elastomer Film*	---	9.25	604
	Silastic® II		
As-Received Shell	---	10.39	921
Extracted Shell	14.7	13.83	1131
Elastomer Film*	---	12.43	1211

*Dispersed elastomeric films of the same batch prepared at the time the implants were originally manufactured.

The cross-link densities, determined from swelling measurements, as a function of implantation time for Silastic® I and Silastic® II shells are shown in Figures 8 and 9, respectively. If the elastomer embrittles, one would expect the cross-link density to increase; a decrease suggests elastomeric network degradation. The cross-link density of the Silastic® I implants is essentially independent of implantation time even after 21 years in vivo. This suggests that the silicone elastomer undergoes little or no change during implantation. The cross-link density of the Silastic® II implants may exhibit a slight increase with implantation time. However, the measured values are within the limits of the experimental error and if any change occurs, it is small. Additional work on this particular issue is needed before a definitive conclusion regarding the long-term durability of Silastic® II implants can be determined.

Fig. 5. MALDI Mass Spectrum from the extract of a Silastic® I silicone/silica shell. The insert shows an expanded view of the mass range from 1150 to 2000 Da.

Fig. 6. Number and weight average molecular weights determined by MALDI-MS from the extract of a Silastic I shell as a function of implantation time.

Fig. 7. Number and weight average molecular weights determined by MALDI-MS from the extract of a Silastic® II shell as a function of implantation time.

Fig. 8. Cross-link density of the silicone/silica shell as a function of implantation time for Silastic® I shells.

Fig. 9. Cross-link density of the silicone/silica shell as a function of implantation time for Silastic® II shells.

SUMMARY

The mechanical and chemical properties of silicone/silica explanted breast implants which have implantation times ranging from zero (controls) to 21 years were studied. Strength, elongation-to-failure, extractables, cross-link density, number and weight averaged molecular weights from extracts were determined. The Silastic® I shells, with no barrier coating, show little change in tensile strength and a slight decrease in elongation even after 21 years in vivo implantation time. Silastic® II shells, containing a barrier coating, exhibit a decrease in strength and elongation with time with a corresponding increase in silicones sorbed from the gel. The data suggest that the overall change in the silicone elastomer of Silastic® II shells is small. The integrity of the barrier coating was not examined and the influence of this coating on the long-term properties of an implant is an open question.

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